

FIBER ORIENTATION ASSESSMENT IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES USING INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

H. Fernandes^{1*}, X. Maldague¹

¹ Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Computer Vision and Systems Laboratory (CVSL), Laval University, Quebec City, Canada

* Corresponding author (henrique-coelho.fernandes.1@ulaval.ca)

Keywords: *carbon/PEEK, fiber orientation assessment, complex shaped parts, non-destructive testing and evaluation, infrared thermography*

Abstract

Infrared thermography is a largely studied technique used for non-destructive testing and evaluation. One of the most popular applications is the assessment of flaws in composite materials. However, in this paper we present another application which aims to assess fiber content in composites instead. More specifically a "laser spot" technique, that we call Pulsed Thermal Ellipsometry (PTE), is used to assess fiber orientation on the surface of a carbon/PEEK (*Polyether ether ketone*) laminate. Incremental changes on the angle of incidence of camera optical axis are used to simulate inspection of complex shaped parts and demonstrate the feasibility of PTE to inspect parts of this type.

1 Introduction

The use of composite materials (CM) is growing more and more every day in several applications, especially in aeronautic structures. The arrangement or orientation of the fibers relative to one another, the fiber concentration, and the distribution all have a significant influence on the strength and other properties of fiber reinforced composites. Thus testing techniques must be developed to assess fiber content. Destructive methods can be employed to evaluate the fiber on a composite, e.g. cutting a section of the material, polishing the area and evaluating it with microscopy. However, the destructive approach is not always an option since the sample will be damaged after inspection and probably unfit for use. Thus, Non-Destructive

Testing and Evaluation (NDT&E) techniques must be employed in some cases to assess the material's fiber content.

Infrared Thermography (IT) is a well-known and widely used NDT&E technique for composite material inspection. In active IT an external heat source is used to stimulate the material being inspected in order to generate a thermal contrast between the feature of interest and the background. The active approach is adopted in many cases given that the inspected parts are usually in equilibrium with the surroundings [1]. Qualitative and quantitative assessment of flaws is a very popular application of IT for CM. However there are others such as fiber orientation assessment. In this work we apply IT to assess fiber orientation on a sample's surface. More specifically a "laser spot" technique, that we call Pulsed Thermal Ellipsometry (PTE), is used to assess fiber orientation on the surface of a carbon/PEEK sample. Incremental changes on the angle of incidence of camera optical axis were used during experiments to simulate the inspection of complex shaped parts demonstrating the feasibility of PTE to inspect complex shaped parts.

2 Pulsed Thermal Ellipsometry - PTE

More than one century ago, De Senarmont [2] applied a thermal approach to determine the principal orientations in crystal plates: he covered them with a thin layer of wax, heated them over a small spot and monitored the isotherm shape

Fig 1 - Thermal analysis laser heat pulse of fiber orientation in composite material

revealed by the solid/liquid transition contour appearing in the wax layer. The isotherm proved to be elliptical and its aspect ratio is related to the square root of the principal conductivities in the surface plane.

This method, referred to later by Krapez [5-8] as “Thermal Ellipsometry”, was later used for various applications (with, of course, up-to-date experimental equipment) by means of thermography. It was applied on polymer materials to establish a correlation between their draw ratio and the induced thermal anisotropy. It was also used to evaluate the fiber orientation in the case of composite materials using short or long carbon fibers. For the latter problem, authors like Aindow [3] and Cielo [4] showed that heat propagates faster in the longitudinal direction of fiber on the surface of fiber reinforced laminates. In [3], Aindow et al. detected local anisotropy in CFRP (nylon-66) injection mouldings by two methods: thermography using infrared scanning, which reveals anisotropy of thermal conductivity, and polarized shear-wave ultrasonic showing elastic anisotropy. For the thermographic method, they recorded isotherms formed around a point source of heat on a plane surface (heat was applied for a period of 15 seconds) using an infrared imaging camera. The isotherms that they observed were ellipses of which the ratio of lengths of the principal axes (b/a) are proportional to the square root of the ratio of thermal conductivities. They assumed that the longest dimension of the

counter in each picture indicated the major axis of thermal conductivity in the surface, which in turn is related to the direction of fiber orientation.

Cielo et al. presented in [4] a comparative review of a number of optical techniques for the characterization of non-metallic materials. One possibility reported by them is the evaluation of phase (or fiber) orientation in stretched polymer films or in composites by an analysis of the thermal propagation pattern. A typical configuration is shown in Fig. 1. They spot-heated the inspected part by a narrow laser beam and the resulting heat-propagation pattern was analyzed by an IR camera. If the material is oriented, such as the unidirectional graphite-epoxy sheet they inspected, an elliptical thermal pattern is observed, with the ratio between the two principal axes (b/a) being related to the square root of the thermal conductivities in the longitudinal and transverse directions. A test on an isotropic material would give a circle instead of an ellipse. They illustrated this approach showing results from two 8-ply unidirectional NARMGO 5217 sheets spot heated for a period of 20 seconds with a 0.5 W laser.

A more detailed theoretical analysis was later undertaken through an analytical treatment of thermal diffusion in laminates made of orthotropic layers assuming the surface is submitted to concentrated heating by Krapez in [5]. Three temporal regimes were considered in that study: steady-state regime, transient regime (as obtained during step heating), and modulated regime (in order to analyze how the so-called thermal waves “propagate” in orthotropic laminates). Experiments were performed on carbon-epoxy laminates for all three regimes. In [6], Krapez used the same theory (thermal anisotropy measurements method which consists in analyzing the shape of the isotherms which develop around a heated spot) to develop a thermal inversion method to infer thickness of skin and core layers of a 3-layer carbon/epoxy laminate.

In [9], Karpen et al. used lock-in thermography (harmonic thermal waves) to probe orientation fields of carbon fibers both along the surface and in depth at low modulation frequencies and within a short time. Later, in [10] he developed a theoretical model in order to correctly interpret the measurements.

3 Numerical simulations

The finite element method is a powerful numerical tool that enables the solution of complex nonlinear, nonsymmetrical mathematical problems governed by partial differential equations such as the one of heat transfer by conduction, convection and radiation with temperature dependent thermal properties of materials involved. In order to solve the given differential equation, a 2D model of the sample's surface geometry corresponding to the tested sample was defined and its calculation domain divided into finite elements that represent base elements on which the equation solutions are found. The numerical modeling was performed using the software COMSOL Multiphysics® 4.3 from Comsol, Inc.

The purpose of this numerical simulation was to verify the feasibility of the PTE for the inspection of materials such as carbon/PEEK. Parameters used in the simulation that concerns heat transfer are

Fig. 2 – 2D simulation of thermal elliptical pattern formation on the surface of an orthotropic material. Fiber is oriented in the direction of the ellipse's major axis as it was expected.

Fig. 3 - Photo of sample's surface

$k_{\parallel} = 5.65 \left(\frac{W}{mK}\right)$ and $k_{\perp} = 0.335 \left(\frac{W}{mK}\right)$ are the thermal conductivity values parallel (y-direction) and perpendicular (x-direction) to the fibers, respectively, $\rho = 1584 \left(\frac{kg}{m^3}\right)$ is the density, $C = 1310 \left(\frac{J}{kg K}\right)$ is the specific heat of the material (taken from Ageorges et al. 1998 [11]). It is not the aim of this paper to discuss the numerical simulation. Thus, just a snapshot of the thermal pattern formed on the surface is shown in Fig. 2. It shows that PTE enables the assessment of fiber orientation on the surface of our Carbon/PEEK laminate.

4 Experiments and Results

The sample used during the experiments is a laminate moulded with Carbon/PEEK plies. It has 48 plies oriented in 0° and 90° directions consecutively ($[(0/90)_{24}]$). The final consolidated plate

Table 1 - Parameters used in the experiment

Parameter	Value
Diode-laser frequency	805 nm
Beam power used	5W of 30W
Shooting duration	0.1 seconds
Spot size on plate's surface	3 mm
Recording time	20 seconds
Image used to extract fiber orientation	0.2 seconds after beam had stopped

Fig. 4 – Experiment set-up

is 5mm thick (thus each ply is approximately 0.125mm thick), it has a length of 5cm and width of 5cm. Fig. 3 shows a picture (in the visible spectrum) of the sample's surface. Notice that the direction of fiber orientation on the first layer was written on the right-bottom corner by the manufacturer.

The sample was inspected by PTE using a diode-laser spot as the stimulation source. The sample was placed in front of the laser beam and a plano-convex lens was placed between the laser beam and the plate. The lens was used to focus the beam in a small spot. The angle of incidence of the laser beam with the plate's surface, i.e. the angle between the incident beam on a surface and the line perpendicular to the surface at the point of incidence, was 0° while the camera optical axis angle of incidence was 15° , i.e. the angle between the camera optical axis and the plate's normal to the surface. A short pulse was shot heating a small circle area on the plate's surface. Then, the heating and cooling down process were recorded using a mid-wave infrared camera (MWIR). As mentioned before, the pattern formed on the plate's surface is elliptical in anisotropic materials, which is the case of Carbon/PEEK composite and the ellipse major axis is related to the fiber orientation. The parameters used in this experiment are listed in Table 1. Fig. 4 shows the experiment set-up.

The experiments were divided into two steps. First, in order to verify if the fiber orientation on the plate's surface was really 0° , we performed the

Fig. 5 – (a) Fiber orientation: 0° . (b) Fiber orientation: 90° .

experiment with the plate positioned as it is in Fig. 3. Thus, the first layer had fibers oriented at 0° with respect to the x-axis. Then, the plate was rotated 90° (clockwise, around the y-axis shown in Fig. 4) in order to have fibers oriented at 90° and we performed the experiment again. Theoretically, the ellipse's major axis of these two measurements should be 90° apart. Second, we kept the sample in one fixed position where fibers in the surface had a 0° orientation with respect to the x-axis. Then, we used incremental changes on the angle of incidence of camera optical axis to evaluate its effect on the thermal pattern formed on the sample's surface and evaluate what would be the maximum angle of incidence that would not make the PTE technique inapplicable (as mentioned before, these angle measurements were performed to determine the feasibility of the technique in inspecting complex shaped parts).

4.1 First experiment

In the first experiment the plate was first heated in a horizontal position (thus the fiber orientation on first layer was 0°) and then heated in a vertical position (rotating it 90° clockwise so that the fiber orientation on the first layer was 90°). This first experiment showed that with the laser spot technique one can

Table 2- Ellipse's major axis orientation measured during the first experiment

Plate's position	Horizontal	Vertical
Measured angle	0.65°	89.52°

Fig. 6 – Angle measurements experimental setup. 2D schema where α is the laser beam angle of incidence and β is the camera optical axis angle of incidence. β ranges from 0° to 75° .

measure the fiber orientation on the surface of a carbon/PEEK plate. Fig. 5 shows each image from each inspection used to analyze the fiber orientation. The ellipse's major axis was drawn on each image and Table 2 shows the ellipse's major angles measured in each inspection.

4.2 Second experiment – angle measurements

In this experiment the plate and laser beam were maintained stationary. The laser beam angle of incidence was 20° in this second experiment. Then, the angle of incidence of the MWIR camera was incrementally increased to conduct angle measurements. For the first measurement the camera optical axis angle of incidence was 0° . Subsequently measurements were carried out increasing the angle of incidence 15° each time. Thus the tested angles were 0° , 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° and 75° . Fig. 6 shows a

Table 3 - Camera rotation x Ellipse orientation

Camera rotation	Ellipse's major axis orientation ¹
0°	-0.05°
15°	-0.17°
30°	-2.59°
45°	-4.63°

¹ regarding x-axis

Fig. 7 – Measured ellipses after 0.2s with four different camera optical axis angle of incidence. Red line indicates ellipse's major axis while the cross represents ellipse centroid. The left image is the original thermogram and the right image is the processed ellipse used to calculate its orientation. Angles of incidence: (a-b) 0° , (c-d) 15° , (e-f) 30° and (g-h) 45°

schematic drawing of the experiment were β is the camera optical axis angle of incidence.

For the second experiment, parameters concerning beam shooting duration, recording time, and others were the same used in the first experiment and are

listed in Table 1. For the six tested angles, the last two did not produced accurate measurements. Thus they are not reported here. Fig. 7 shows the ellipses for each successful measured angle (thermal image and correspondent ellipse) and Table 3 shows for each tested angle of incidence its respective ellipse orientation related to the fiber orientation on the first layer, that is 0° .

An extra test was performed at the end of this experiment. The effect of changing the laser beam angle of incidence was briefly investigated. Previously, the camera optical axis angle of incidence was changing and the laser angle of incidence was maintained stationary (20° angle with plate's normal to the surface). Now for this test, we kept the camera stationary and increased the laser beam angle of incidence. The goal of this test was to check the maximum angle between the laser beam and the plate's normal to the surface which would not render the technique unfeasible. It can be concluded that PTE works well up to 60° for the laser beam angle of incidence. In Fig. 8, for example, the laser beam angle of incidence was $\alpha=75^\circ$. When α is above 60° , there was not enough heat hitting the surface in order to produce the elliptical pattern. Thus, since there is no ellipse, it is not possible to calculate the fiber orientation by PTE.

Fig. 8 - High laser beam angle of incidence do not generate enough heat on plate's surface for the PTE technique. In this case $\alpha=75^\circ$

5 Discussion

The first experiment confirmed what was expected from the literature and from numerical simulation. Fig. 5 shows the same position of the plate's surface heated while the sample was in two different positions: horizontal and vertical. In that case the ellipse's orientation is expected to be 90° apart. Measurements showed the ellipses to be 88.87° apart. This error of 1.13° is negligible and we consider PET a reasonable technique for fiber orientation measurement.

The second experiment was designed to stress the technique in terms of its capability measuring complex shaped parts. A flat sample was used in the experiments thus incremental increases on the camera optical axis angle of incidence were used to simulate measurements in angled parts. It can be said that even with an angle of incidence greater than 0° , the fiber orientation on the plate's surface can still be measured with PTE. It can also be said from the measured ellipses that the smaller the angle of incidence, the more precise the ellipse orientation will be, regarding fiber orientation. For example, in the second experiment the fiber orientation on the surface was 0° with respect to the x-axis. PTE measurement conducted with an angle of incidence of 0° resulted a measured ellipse orientation of -0.05° (very close to 0°) while with an angle of incidence of 45° the measured ellipse had an orientation of -4.63° (but still close to 0°).

The orientation of the ellipse's major axis is expected to be shifted when it is a change on the camera optical axis angle of incidence (such as in the case of the experiment reported in Table 3). This is due to the perspective effect. A picture taken from a front view will be separated by a perspective projection (a matrix multiplication) from a picture taken in an angled view. The script used to calculate the ellipse's orientation treats both images in a similar manner. Thus, a (small) difference in the ellipse's major axis orientation is expected.

Fig. 9 – Possible set-up for fiber orientation measurement in a complex shaped part.

In a central projection camera model, a three-dimensional point in space is projected onto the image plane by means of straight visual rays from the point in space to the optical center (such as the human eye). This process can be described mathematically by a projection matrix P , which takes a point in three-dimensional space and transforms it into a point on the two-dimensional image plane. The projection matrix P can be computed from the external and internal camera parameters, such as its position, orientation and focal length.

In the case where planar surfaces are imaged, the transformation is called a plane-to-plane homography (a simpler matrix H). If the homography between a plane in the scene and the plane of the image is known, then the image of the planar surface can be rectified into a front-on view. The homography can be computed simply by knowing the relative position of four points on the scene plane and their corresponding positions in the image [12]. Thus, the small error reported in Table 3 may be corrected by applying a homography in the infrared image before extracting the ellipse's orientation.

6 Conclusions and future work

In this work infrared thermography was used for non-destructive characterization of composite materials. The feasibility of Pulsed Thermal Ellipsometry (PTE using a laser spot pulse as

excitation source) was tested and shown to measure fiber orientation on the surface of a carbon/PEEK specimen. Angle measurements, due to changes on the angle of incidence of the camera optical axis, were performed in order to simulate the evaluation of complex shaped parts (angled parts). It was shown that it is possible to measure fiber orientation precisely up to a certain angle of incidence. Fig. 9 shows a schematic example of a L-bracket part inspection that could be conducted using PTE. Future work includes investigation of the potential of angle measurements to assess fiber orientation in deeper layers.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to greatly acknowledge financial support provided by Laval University and the industrial partners: Bell Helicopter Textron Canada Limited, Bombardier Inc., Pratt and Whitney Canada Corp., Marquez Transtech Limited, Delastek Inc. and Avior Integrated Products Inc.

The authors would also like to acknowledge the funding provided by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), the Consortium for Research and Innovation in Aerospace in Quebec (CRIAQ COMP-412), the *Fonds québécois de la recherche sur la nature et les technologies* (FQRNT) and National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (*CNPq*) a Brazilian governmental agency.

References

- [1] X. Maldague "Theory and practice of infrared technology for nondestructive testing". John Wiley & Sons, New York, 2001.
- [2] M. H. De Senarmont "Mémoire sur la conductibilité des substances cristallisées pour la chaleur". *Second Mémoire, Annales de Chimie Physique*, Vol. 3, 22, pp 179-211, 1851.

- [3] J.D. Aindow, M.F. Markhan, K.E. Puttick, J.G. Rider and M.R. Rudman "Fibre orientation detection in injection-moulded carbon fibre reinforced components by thermography and ultrasonics". *NDT international*, Vol. 19, No. 1, pp 24-29, 1986.
- [4] P. Cielo, X. Maldague, J.-C. Krapez and R. Lewak "Optics-Based Techniques for the Characterization of Composites and Ceramics". *Nondestructive Characterization of Metals*; Montreal; Canada, pp 733-744, 1987.
- [5] J.-C. Krapez "Thermal ellipsometry applied to the evaluation of fibre orientation in composites". *Journee d'Etude sur la Thermographie*, Paris, France, 1994-171, 1994.
- [6] J.-C. Krapez "Thermal ellipsometry- A tool applied for in-depth resolved characterization of fibre orientation in composites". *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, Seattle, WA, July 30-Aug. 4, 1995, ONERA, TP, n.1995-148, 1995.
- [7] J.-C. Krapez, G. Gardette, and D. Balageas "Thermal ellipsometry in steady-state and by lock-in thermography. Application to anisotropic materials characterization". In: D. Balageas, G. Busse, G.M. Carlomagno, editors. *Proceedings of the Qirt 96*, Eurotherm Series 50. EETI ed., pp. 257-262, 1996.
- [8] J.-C. Krapez and G. Gardette "Characterisation of anisotropic materials by steady-state and modulated thermal ellipsometry". *High Temperatures - High Pressures*, v.30(5), pp. 567-574, 1998.
- [9] W. Karpen, D. Wu, R. Steegmuller and G. Busse "Depth profiling of orientation in laminates with local lock-in thermography", in: D. Balageas, G. Busse, G.M. Carlomagno, editors. *Proceedings of the Qirt 94*, Eurotherm Series 42, EETI editions, pp. 281-286, 1994.
- [10] W. Karpen, D. Wu, and G. Busse "A Theoretical Model for the Measurement of Fiber Orientation with Thermal Waves". *Res. Nondestr. Eval.*, v. 11, pp. 179-197, 1999.
- [11] C. Ageorges, L. Ye, Y.-M. Mai and M. Houe "Characteristics of resistance welding of lap shear coupons: Part I: Heat transfer". *Composites*, 29A, pp 899-909, 1998.
- [12] D. A. Forsyth, and J. Ponce "*Computer Vision: A Modern Approach*". Upper Saddle River, J: Prentice-Hall, 2003.